

Understanding and Perceived Challenges to the Mandanas Ruling Among Barangay Officials in Solano, Nueva Vizcaya

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Abstract. This paper evaluates the understanding of barangay officials regarding the Mandanas Ruling, including their perceived challenges related to the crafting and planning of their own transition plans, revenue and fiscal matters. The paper employs a mixed-methods approach, combining quantitative and qualitative research designs, and utilizing a descriptive methodology and thematic analysis. The findings reveal that barangay officials are generally familiar with the provisions and implications of the ruling. The data also reveal no significant difference in the understanding of the Ruling regarding transition plans and revenue and fiscal matters based on the officials' position, years of service, and the number of seminars attended. Although, a significant difference in the understanding of revenue and fiscal matters concerning the number of seminars attended by barangay officials has been observed. Drawing more to the realities of the local operations, the respondents remain heavily dependent on their national tax allotment (NTA) and lack income-generating projects that could sustain their local operations independently. Despite their familiarity with the ruling, the paper indicates potential challenges in its full implementation. As additional functions and services are devolved to barangays alongside increased budget allocations, local officials anticipate higher budgetary requirements or financial requirements for them to effectively cater or deliver all devolved functions and services. The respondents also expected to increase the workload and responsibilities, necessitating enhanced capacity-building initiatives to equip them with the competencies required to perform their expanded functions. Furthermore, the increased allocation of public funds entails the need for stronger accountability and transparency mechanisms to ensure the efficient and responsible utilization of resources.

Keywords: fiscal devolution; internal revenue allotment; local government; Mandanas-Garcia Ruling; national tax allotment

Introduction

Tax is the lifeblood of the government and of the economy. It is by no means a simple matter. Tax is arguably one of the most frustrating and interesting aspects of governance, and improving our tax system is a continuing debate every fiscal year. Thirty years after the Local Government Code (LGC) was enacted, the nation struggles and is still closely dependent on the National Government (NG). In most cases, it is immensely backtracked. The local government sector has considered this and has long called for fiscal devolution.

Since it became final and executory on April 10, 2019, the Mandanas-Garcia Ruling has gradually begun to be implemented nationwide. The ruling concluded two separate petitions filed by the namesakes: Governor Hermilando Mandanas of Batangas and Former Bataan Governor, the late Enrique Garcia Jr.

Both petitions were filed to challenge how the NG was going about computing the Internal Revenue Allotment (IRA) shares of the Local Governments (LG); particularly, the petitioners pleaded to the Supreme Court (SC) to mandate this process based on what they termed as "Just Shares" of the LGUs. The SC ruled that the determination of the mentioned just shares of LGUs should not be based solely on the national internal revenue alone but on all national taxes from all government tax-collecting agencies. It also declared "Internal Revenue" written in section 284 of the LGC of 1991 unconstitutional, ordering it to be removed entirely.

Figure 1. LGU Shares in National Taxes
From Graphics from the Mandanas-Garcia Ruling website

The ruling thus becomes a pivotal legal decision that has significant implications for local governance in the country. It redefines the fiscal autonomy of LGUs, including the smallest unit—the Barangays. As Diaz-Manalo et. al. (2021) stated, “the Ruling redefined the computation of the IRA, supporting the inclusion of all national taxes, not just national internal revenue taxes.” The new computation is comprehensively shown in Figure 1. The Ruling will have an immense impact on the municipalities and other smaller units as they will be subjected to various challenges as supported by a study conducted by Silva (2005), which explains that “by establishing a system of patronage and reliance between the national and local governments, devolution has not lessened regional imbalances but rather strengthened them.” With the full implementation of the Mandanas-Garcia Ruling, the LGUs are expected to alleviate poverty gradually, considering their self-sufficient progress through their revenue-generating projects and the increase in their allocation from the national government.

As the shares of LGUs from the national taxes increase, this will mean additional financial resources and bigger responsibilities. The national government will fully devolve the basic services and facilities to local governments, as Section 17 of the LGC stipulates. Specific examples of expenditure responsibilities by local government units that will be affected after the Mandanas Ruling are shown in Figure 2. For a barangay, examples of this include agricultural support services, health and social welfare services such as health centers and day-care centers, information and reading centers, services and facilities related to general hygiene and solid waste collection, maintenance of barangay roads and bridges, and infrastructure facilities such as halls, pavements, plazas, sports centers, among others.

Health & Social Services	Agriculture	Environmental Protection & Management	Infrastructure	Tourism	Regulatory Functions
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Primary health care Maternal and child care Disease control services Purchase of medicines, medical supplies, and equipment Social welfare services for children, youth, family, community, women, elderly, disabled persons, rebel returnees and evacuees; Relief operations; Population development Socialized housing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Inter-barangay irrigation system Water and soil resource utilization and conservation projects Enforcement of fishery laws in municipal waters Conservation of mangroves 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Solid waste disposal system General hygiene and sanitation Community-based forestry projects Management and control of communal forests 	<p>Provision for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Public markets Public buildings Freedom parks and other public assembly areas Other similar facilities <p>Maintenance and rehabilitation of:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Roads and bridges, School buildings and other facilities for basic education Clinics, health centers and other health facilities Fish ports Artesian wells Water supply systems Seawalls and dikes Drainage and sewerage Flood control system Traffic signals and road signs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Development of tourism facilities and other tourist attractions Acquisition of equipment Regulation and supervision of business concessions 	<p>Certain regulatory functions of the national government:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Inspection of food products Adoption of quarantine regulations Enforcement of the National Building Code Regulations of transport operations Licensing of cockpits

Figure 2. Expenditure Responsibilities of local government units
From Bureau of Local Government Finance. *Income Profile of Local Government Units 2009-2014.*

Thus, barangay officials play a fundamental role in local governance, acting as the frontline representatives of the community and implementing policies and initiatives that have the potential to impact the residents' daily lives. As supported by Boysillo (2017), "the barangay, as a primary implementing unit, is mandated to plan and develop projects and programs and implement government policies and activities in the community, create projects within its territory and to deliver basic services of the government to the people. This will also benefit the constituents of the localities because they will see better how local governments fulfill their duties through their activities and allocations."

Like any natural crisis during typhoons and earthquakes, the pandemic has proved that the local government units best respond quickly to constituents. While we have seen initiatives from different cities to their response during the pandemic, many LGUs faced a lack of financial capacity to provide basic services.

The researchers take Solano, a first-class municipality of Nueva Vizcaya, known as the booming commercial capital, premier urban center, and one of the fastest-growing municipalities in Region II, had issues implementing their projects and programs as stated in their executive summary.

According to their Executive Summary report to the Commission on Audit (COA) for the last five years (2018-2022), an independent auditor had various significant findings on their financial statements. It found that there were unreliable balances due to a network account that was unreconciled in the general ledger and reports; receivable accounts that were dormant due to failure of management to enforce collection or liquidation from recipients; doubtful balances of accounts due to unsupported valid claims and documentations and misclassifications; unguaranteed implementation of programs and projects and the settlement of liabilities; unsettled audit disallowances; and unliquidated cash advances.

More so, there was the inability to completely implement and deliver identified programs, activities, and projects (PAPs) for current year and the continuing appropriations; unoptimized and unmaximized use of available appropriations for the 70-percent Mitigation Fund, Continuing Appropriation and Special Trust Fund with an unexpended balance; erroneous accounting treatment of Real Property Taxes and Special Education Taxes collected in advance which resulted into abnormal balances and misstatements of the affected Receivable accounts, Deferred Income accounts, tax revenues in the financial statements; unrecorded costs for on-going construction projects.

Erroneous treatment of subsidies to LGUs instead of Due to LGUs, recording Donations and Grants instead of Due to National Government Agencies (NGAs), recording an item as Other Maintenance and Other Operating Expense instead of capitalizing it as part of the PPE; outright expense without any liquidation documents; claims unsupported with proof of computations and actual physical reporting; no property ledger cards or subsidiary ledgers maintained for the construction in progress and PPE; not prepared bank reconciliation statements of the development fund; doubtful existence, condition, and propriety of the PPE; and not complied mandatory requirement of allocation at least five-percent of the total appropriations for Gender and Development PAPs were also found.

Thus, resulting in contraries or violations to presidential decrees, COA circulars, manual for NGAS, and the local government code before the Municipalities' misappropriation, misallocation, mismatched, unrecorded, and unliquidated accounts. With regards to the Mandanas Ruling, the provincial government of Nueva Vizcaya has already crafted its own Provincial Executive Order and Sangguniang Panlalawigan Resolution, localizing their own Devolution Transition Committee as a response to the national government's issuance of E.O. No. 138 s. 2021 or the full devolution of certain functions of the executive branch to local governments, creation of a committee on devolution, and for other purposes; DILG-DBM JMC 2021-01 or the guidelines on the preparation of devolution Transition Plans of local government units in support of full devolution under E.O. No. 138; and other laws in preparation for the implementation of the full devolution.

In the assessment of the provincial government, some devolved basic services and functions of other sectors from the LGC are still not being performed by Nueva Vizcaya, such as the medical laboratory services, comprehensive program for street children, half-way house of rebel returnees, monitoring of health facilities, and lot more not assumed services and functions in various sectors. This strengthens the rationale for studying the barangays' knowledge and challenges to the ruling on what functions should be devolved to them by the province for the next few years. As to Cruz et al. (2022), "the larger the LGUs budget, the lower the rate of budget utilization. Cities and provinces, on average, have Php 604 million unspent per year, with some LGUs exceeding Php 8 billion unspent in one year. Furthermore, the size of the capital outlay budgets is negatively correlated with the budget utilization rate (BUR) of LGUs". Thus, the United Nations Development Programme Philippines would suggest that "a new approach to building public financial management capacity needs to be adopted to prevent further underspending after the Mandanas-Garcia transition."

Glancing the IRA in 2022, the Senate Economic Planning Office (SEPO) views that "LGUs in the Philippines have been clamoring for more fiscal transfers to address some of the challenges they have been facing." SEPO cited World Bank that "studies have attributed poor budget spending and Local Development

Fund (LDF) utilization rates to various reasons such as (1) limited implementation capacity, (2) inadequate planning and program prioritization, (3) weak competencies in public financial management, (4) lack of manpower, and (5) process bottlenecks such as in procurement. There is an apprehension that unless these issues are addressed, a significant increase in the local budget due to the Ruling may result in even worse underspending.”

Gonzales (2020) cited the Department of Interior and Local Government (DILG) reporting that “183 barangay executives in the country were under investigation by the Philippine National Police-Criminal Investigation and Detection Group for alleged graft and corruption in the distribution of the social amelioration program in the year 2020.” Therefore, another challenge that might persist is corruption. Therefore, it explains that as LGUs will be provided higher coffers, there will also be consequences of devolving a wider scope of responsibilities to them, expecting them to be more productive and progressive regarding their duties, plans, and actions. With these concerns, it is clear that there were perceived inconsistencies and concerns that alarms the LGUs that has to be fixed in order for the Mandanas-Garcia Ruling to prosper the way it should be. Since the Ruling has just been recently ruled out, there are few significant studies about the Ruling itself, considering the Executive Order No. 138 issued by Former President Rodrigo Duterte on June 1, 2021, wherein devolved functions, services, and facilities per Section 17 of Republic Act No. 7160 and other pertinent laws shall be fully devolved from the NG to the LGUs no later than Fiscal Year 2024. Therefore, it has not yet been fully implemented. However, LGUs are still crafting their tax codes or preparing other necessary processes before implementing them.

Research Questions

This study seeks to determine the level of understanding of Solano Nueva Vizcaya barangay officials to the Mandanas Ruling and their perceived challenges to its implementation.

Specifically, it answers the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1 positions;
 - 1.2 years of service and
 - 1.3 How many seminars were attended related to the Mandanas Ruling and fiscal devolution?
2. What is the level of understanding of barangay officials of Solano, Nueva Vizcaya, on the implementation of Mandanas Ruling in terms of:
 - 2.1 Transition Plans; and
 - 2.2 Revenue and Fiscal Matters?
3. Is there a significant difference in the level of understanding of the barangay officials of Solano, Nueva Vizcaya to the Mandanas Ruling in terms of Transition Plans, Revenue, and Fiscal Matters to their positions, years of service, and number of seminars attended related to the Mandanas Ruling or fiscal devolution?
4. What are the perceived challenges of Solano, Nueva Vizcaya's barangay officials to the Mandanas Ruling?
5. What are the expected outputs to help barangay officials of Solano, Nueva Vizcaya in their level of understanding and perceived challenges to the Mandanas Ruling?

Literature Review

Fiscal Devolution

The Mandanas Ruling significantly increases the share of national taxes allocated to LGUs. This aims to empower LGUs by facilitating the full devolution of basic service delivery outlined in the Local Government Code. The Ruling represents a major step towards fiscal devolution. “Devolution is the transfer of power and authority from the national government to the local government units” (Tabunda and Galang, 1991). Therefore, fiscal devolution is defined in this study as “the transfer of resources from higher to lower levels of governments usually accompanied by an enhancement in responsibilities and functions” (Khan, 2001). Ongaro (2006) mentioned that in Italy, “the requirements for an effective implementation of devolution are radical alteration of programmatic activities, workforce alignment, and structural arrangements” (as cited in Teng-Calleja, 2016). Moreover, Arnaboldi and Lapsey (2003) included the key elements of reforming financial and human resource management in transforming local governments in the United Kingdom. The Philippines is not detached from the challenges of devolution even with a three-decade history of local governance empowerment.

Transition Plans

Diaz-Manalo et al. (2021) stated, "Aside from fiscal considerations, the transition calls for examining PAPs to be devolved. There are concerns about how the intended outcomes can be achieved as NG transfers to LGUs and some of the PAPs it continues to perform despite being devolved functions. The transition towards full devolutions assumes capacitating LGUs. It is in the interest of the NG to ensure that a system for capacity-building is in place for LGUs to manage the devolved functions effectively." Therefore, there is also a great concern about transitioning the devolved functions and responsibilities in its implementation. However, Cruz (2023) cited the Department of Interior and Local Government (DILG) recommended that "the period of devolving more responsibilities from NGs to LGs be moved from 2024 to 2027 to allow the creation of offices that would deliver the functions and services devolved to the LGs." In addition, DILG Undersecretary for Local Government Marlo Iringan recognized the different capacities and challenges different LGs face. It can be perceived that the Transition Plans set by the Duterte administration were not enough for the LGUs to prepare them for the full devolution of basic services.

Revenue and Fiscal Matters

Gulane and Viray (2023) cited Brillantes (1998), who mentioned: "that one of his concerns pertain to whether the Internal Revenue Allotment share of the local government was indeed sufficient to cover the development functions of the local government, considering the bulk of personnel devolved them." Thus, it connotes doubts that funds were insufficient to cater to its constituents' needs. The problem mentioned by Capuno (2017) that "Philippine devolution did not fully consider the idea of 'finance follows function,' given that arrangement on the distribution of fiscal resources through the IRA were determined first before the expenditure assignments, is an underlying weakness of the setups." However, to reiterate Diaz-Manalo et al. (2021) stated that "although the IRA will significantly increase (on aggregate) beginning 2022, it will not address the inherent inequities brought about by the existing distribution formula." With these concerns, it is clear that there were perceived inconsistencies and concerns that alarm the LGUs and must be fixed for the Mandanas-Garcia Ruling to prosper as it should.

Methodology

Research Design

This study used quantitative and qualitative design. For the quantitative part, the descriptive method was utilized for the profile variables and the level of understanding of the Mandanas Ruling in terms of Transition Plans and Revenue and Fiscal Matters. Meanwhile, when grouped according to profile variables, a comparative method was used to determine the significant difference in understanding the Mandanas Ruling regarding Transition Plans and Revenue and Fiscal Matters. For the qualitative part, descriptive method and thematic analysis were used to assess the perceived challenges in implementing the Mandanas Ruling. The techniques for gathering data were through surveys and interviews with selected key informants. Salient findings were used to craft the infographics and PowerPoint containing information about the Mandanas Ruling.

Sampling Design

This study employed a purposive sampling procedure as it focuses on the barangay officials who will implement the said ruling in their respective constituents. Specifically, the six barangays divided to the top three highest and top three lowest based on population and income.

Research Locale

According to the municipal website, Solano is a first-class municipality in the province of Nueva Vizcaya, where it is best known as the center of commerce and trade. Solano, being the center of growth, is evidenced by the huge influx of operating businesses within the locality. The Internal Revenue Allotment aids continued exponential growth as the municipality is reported to be 56.7 percent dependent on its shares, in which much is utilized to invest in constructions and facilities that would further foster economic improvement. Solano is also projected to be the next and fifth city in Cagayan Valley and the first in Nueva Vizcaya. The 2022 Cities and Municipalities Index ranked it the 30th most competitive in 1st-2nd class municipalities under economic dynamism. As an economic hub, Solano is the prime locale for conducting the study regarding the Mandanas-Garcia ruling. It allowed the researchers to explore the preparedness of the most affluent municipality in the region regarding the ruling. Specifically, the researchers selected six barangays from the municipality, including Barangays Bagahabag, San Luis, Quezon, Bangar, PD Galima, and Poblacion South.

Research Participants

The participants of this study comprised the newly elected officials of 6 barangays out of the 22 barangays in Solano, Nueva Vizcaya. The researchers considered the highest and lowest extremes, accounting for the barangay's net income for 2022, as the most recent Income Computation Report provided by the Barangay Bookkeeper of the said municipality. The top barangays are Bagahabag, San Luis, and Quezon while placing in the lowest are Bangar, PD Galima, and Poblacion South. This implies that these barangays hold the highest rank in terms of economic status and, thus, will be the most affected by the ruling. Meanwhile, the latter three represent the indigents among the barangays.

Research Instrument

This study used a researcher-made questionnaire composed of two parts. The first part is a four-point Likert scale—fashioned with Very, Familiar, Slightly, and Very Unfamiliar—that evaluated their understanding of their Transition Plans and Revenue and Fiscal Matters. The first section, Transition Plans, comprised items asking whether or not there is a need to develop a transition strategy to be able to identify the gaps and how to address them gradually and whether the submitted devolution Transition Plans (DTP) of the barangay to the Department of Budget Management. This section seeks answers to whether or not the officials understand the procedure of making the DTP and what the plan implies to the barangay. The second section, Revenue and Fiscal Matters included questions that will help researchers answer whether or not officials understand the revenue and fiscal implications of the ruling for the barangay. Such items included are if they understand that only 20 percent, or the smallest percentage, is allocated for the barangays from the national tax allotment or that there is a basis on the allocation, which makes tax allocations different from other barangays. The second part of the questionnaire was an open-ended question asking about the perceived barangay concerns on implementing the Mandanas-Garcia ruling, allowing the researchers a first-hand perspective of the barangay officials regarding the ruling.

Data Gathering Procedure

The data-gathering procedure begun with the purposive sampling of the respondents. This study will include the barangay officials of the six barangays of Solano, Nueva Vizcaya, which are in the top three highest and top three lowest based on population and income. The researchers opted to be the respondents of this study to have a representation from both urbanized and indigent barangays in assessing their level of understanding, which could be more beneficial for this study. Under their office, the respondents in this study should know the Mandanas Ruling (E.O. 138) as the main implementers on the ground level. The researchers of this study personally consulted the offices regarding their participation. Office approval was the green light for the respondents to disseminate the questionnaires with the attached informed consent form. Once all responses have been considered, follow-up interviews were conducted. All the responses were gathered and processed to be used as data for this study.

Results and Discussions

Research Question 1: What is the profile of the respondents in terms of positions, years of service and How many seminars were attended related to the Mandanas Ruling and fiscal devolution?

According to the data, half of the respondents are barangay kagawads. In contrast, the rest of them have equal number of participants, including the barangay chairman, barangay secretary, barangay treasurer, and Sangguniang Kabataan chairman. Most of them has only 1 to 3 years of service and have only 1 to 2 seminars attended related to Mandanas Ruling and Fiscal Devolution.

Research Question 2: What is the level of understanding of barangay officials of Solano, Nueva Vizcaya, on the implementation of Mandanas Ruling in terms of Transition Plans, and Revenue and Fiscal Matters?

Table 1. Level of Understanding on the Implementation of Mandanas Ruling in terms of Transition Plans

	Indicators	Mean	SD	Qualitative Description
1	A transition strategy is employed to achieve full devolution of service from the national government to the local government.	2.67	.83	Familiar
2	The Devolution Transition Plans is submitted before the new barangay officials come into power.	2.56	.82	Familiar
3	The Devolution Transition Plans of barangays is in close coordination with the pertinent National Government Agencies concerned, especially on devolved functions and services critical to them.	2.58	.89	Familiar
4	The Devolution Transition Plans include the state of devolved functions, services, and facilities to local governments.	2.60	.89	Familiar
5	The transition period is three years according to the first executive order released.	2.73	.81	Familiar
	Overall Mean	2.62	.778	Familiar

It appears in Table 1 that the respondents' level of understanding of the implementation of the Mandanas Ruling in terms of Transition Plans is familiar as evidenced by the overall mean of 2.62 and an SD of 0.778. Therefore, the respondents understand the Mandanas Ruling in terms of Transition Plans, since they are familiar with the three-year transition period as to the first executive order released ($\bar{x}=2.73$; $Sd=0.81$); the transition strategy ($\bar{x}=2.67$; $SD=0.83$); the inclusion of the state of devolved functions, services, and facilities to local governments as part of the Devolution Transition Plans (DTP) ($\bar{x}=2.60$; $SD=0.89$); the DTP of barangays that it should be in close coordination with the pertinent National Government Agencies concerned ($\bar{x}=2.58$; $SD=0.89$); and the DTP necessary to be submitted before their term of office ($\bar{x}=2.56$; $SD=0.82$).

Table 2. Level of Understanding on the Implementation of Mandanas Ruling in terms of Revenue and Fiscal Matters

	Indicators	Mean	SD	Qualitative Description
1	A fixed amount is distributed to barangays as part of their share from the national taxes.	2.83	.97	Familiar
2	Aside from the fixed amount, the remaining share for barangays is allocated based on population and equal sharing only.	2.69	.94	Familiar
3	A supplementary funding called Growth Equity Fund will be given to barangays who are financially incapable of allocating and technically weak in implementation of devolved services.	2.56	.92	Familiar
4	The local development fund will be from the national tax allotment.	2.85	1.01	Familiar
5	The Mandanas Ruling supports the economic development of barangays.	2.85	.96	Familiar
	Overall Mean	2.75	.893	Familiar

With an overall mean of 2.75 and an SD of 0.893, Table 2 shows that the respondents are familiar with their understanding of implementing the Mandanas Ruling regarding its Revenue and Fiscal Matters. It emerged that the respondents understand the Revenue and Fiscal Matters, including the local development fund which will come from the national tax allotment ($\bar{x}=2.85$; $SD=1.01$); the context that the Ruling supports the economic development of barangays ($\bar{x}=2.85$; $SD=0.96$); the fixed amount distributed to barangays as their share from the National Government ($\bar{x}=2.83$; $SD=0.97$); the remaining share, aside from the fixed amount, is allocated to them based on population and equal sharing only ($\bar{x}=2.69$; $SD=0.94$); and the supplementary finding called Growth Equity Fund ($\bar{x}=2.56$; $SD=0.92$).

Research Question 3: Is there a significant difference in the level of understanding of the barangay officials of Solano, Nueva Vizcaya to the Mandanas Ruling in terms of Transition Plans, Revenue, and Fiscal Matters to their positions, years of service, and number of seminars attended related to the Mandas Ruling or fiscal devolution?

Table 3. Transition Plans and Positions

Positions	N	Mean	SD	Qualitative Description	Kruskal Wallis	p-value	Decision
Barangay Chairman	6	2.90	.91	Familiar	3.340	.503	Accept Ho
Barangay Kagawad	24	2.67	.85	Familiar			
Barangay Secretary	6	2.80	.76	Familiar			
Barangay Treasurer	6	2.32	.36	Slightly Familiar			
SK Chairperson	6	2.20	.20	Slightly Familiar			

Table 4. Revenue and Fiscal Matters and Positions

Positions	N	Mean	SD	Qualitative Description	Kruskal Wallis	p-value	Decision
Barangay Chairman	6	2.66	1.21	Familiar	2.596	.627	Accept Ho
Barangay Kagawad	24	2.77	.95	Familiar			
Barangay Secretary	6	3.20	.76	Familiar			
Barangay Treasurer	6	2.72	.60	Familiar			
SK Chairperson	6	2.36	.43	Slightly Familiar			

Since the p-value computed for both variables were greater than 0.05, Tables 3 and 4 indicate no significant difference in the responses; hence, the null hypothesis is accepted. This implies that positions do not affect the barangay officials' level of understanding of the Mandanas Ruling in terms of transition plans and revenue and fiscal matters.

Table 5. Transition Plans and Years of Service

Years of Service	N	Mean	SD	Qualitative Description	Kruskal Wallis	p-value	Decision
1-3 years	19	2.31	.77	Slightly Familiar	6.853	.077	Accept Ho
4-6 years	12	2.68	.70	Familiar			
7-9 years	4	2.75	.37	Familiar			
10 years and above	13	3.00	.82	Familiar			

Table 6. Revenue and Fiscal Matters and Years of Service

Years of Service	N	Mean	SD	Qualitative Description	Kruskal Wallis	p-value	Decision
1-3 years	19	2.42	.91	Slightly Familiar	4.477	.214	Accept Ho
4-6 years	12	2.85	.93	Familiar			
7-9 years	4	3.05	.55	Familiar			
10 years and above	13	3.07	.81	Familiar			

Tables 5 and 6 show that the p-value generated was higher than 0.05. Thus, there is no significant difference in the responses; hence, the null hypothesis is accepted. This indicates that years of service do not affect the barangay officials' level of understanding of the Mandanas Ruling in terms of transition plans and revenue and fiscal matters.

Table 7. Transition Plans and the Numbers of Seminars Attended Related to Mandanas Ruling and Fiscal Devolution

Numbers of Seminars Attended	N	Mean	SD	Qualitative Description	Kruskal Wallis	p-value	Decision
None	19	2.28	.70	Slightly Familiar	6.725	.81	Accept Ho
1-2	22	2.84	.80	Familiar			
3-4	2	2.50	.70	Familiar			
5 and above	5	3.04	.55	Familiar			

Table 8. Revenue and Fiscal Matters and the Numbers of Seminars Attended Related to Mandanas Ruling and Fiscal Devolution

Numbers of Seminars Attended	N	Mean	SD	Qualitative Description	Kruskal Wallis	p-value	Decision
None	19	2.38	.86	Slightly Familiar	9.316	.025	Reje
1-2	22	2.89	.85	Familiar			
3-4	2	2.50	.70	Familiar			
5 and above	5	3.68	.52	Very Familiar			

Table 7 presents that with a p-value of 0.81, which is greater than 0.05, there is no significant difference in the responses. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted. This inferred that the number of seminars attended related to the Mandanas Ruling and Fiscal Devolution did not affect the barangay officials' understanding of the Mandanas Ruling regarding Transition Plans. Meanwhile, it can be noted that Table 8 has the only reverse indication as the p-value computed is 0.05. Therefore, there is a significant difference in the responses, so the

null hypothesis is rejected. This implies that seminars attended related to the Mandanas Ruling and Fiscal Devolution affect the level of understanding in terms of Revenue and Fiscal Matters.

Research Question 4: What are the perceived challenges of Solano, Nueva Vizcaya's barangay officials to the Mandanas Ruling?

Various challenges were perceived by the respondents on implementing the Mandanas Ruling, in which four themes are recognized as the most significant concerns necessary to be recognized and fixed by the National Government in the realization of the full implementation of the Mandanas Ruling to the Local Government Units. The researchers categorized them as follows: Plans follow Finance (Budgetary Requirements), Finance follows Responsibilities (Higher Responsibility), Responsibilities follow Furnishing (Pieces of training or Seminars), and Furnishing follows Accountability (Misuse of Funds).

A. Plans follow Finance (Budgetary Requirements)

While the financial aspect is expected to get higher along with implementing the Mandanas Ruling, the decision to fully devolve functions and services to the LGUs became one of their perceived challenges, specifically in meeting the budgetary requirements of the extensive preparation and equipping of manpower and resources.

In the budgetary requirements, the collected responses are regarding the insufficient funds to cater to certain national functions and services from the National Government. Eight of the barangay officials said it is a major challenge for them. Wherein along with this, the researchers recognized four sub-themes categorized as budgetary requirements on the full devolution of functions and services, necessary budget to train personnel, unequal allotment due to varying population size, and expensive training/seminar fees.

A barangay chairman said, "The most challenging [part of the Mandanas Ruling] is to meet the budgetary requirements for the devolved functions." He further expounded his point by illustrating, for instance, various sectors:

Say, for instance, lahat devolve na sana eh, wala naman kaming doctor (*Suppose everything should have been devolved for health, but we do not have doctors*). In the health center, it's good that we have one nurse; all the rest are barangay health workers. We need to train our barangay health workers because they are the frontliners, eh we need money to train them. We have to train our peace and order, our tanods, to meet the demands of rescue, disaster, and everything. So, that is the problem I foresee. That is why if there is a delayed implementation, we can at least slowly capacitate everyone. You cannot do anything if you don't have the capacity.

Meanwhile, a barangay kagawad said that it is one of the disadvantages of the Mandanas Ruling, "Kung maliit yung population mo lesser yung share mo, and kung mas malaki ang population mas malaki rin" (*if a barangay has a small population, it will have a lesser share, and if one has a bigger population, it will have higher funds as well*). Upon observation, certain barangays in the municipality receive lower allotment because their area is mostly surrounded by business establishments and/or dormitories that do not add up to their population. Wherein according to the Mandanas Ruling, the share of each barangay is computed as follows: (1) Php 80,000 for each barangay with a population of not less than one hundred (100) inhabitants, and (2) the balance is allocated as follows: Population – 60% and Equal Sharing – 40%. It shows that the population of a barangay matters to how much they will receive from their National Tax Allotment.

Carrizo (2022) found that "for the local officials in island barangays [of Northern Samar], the question is even more of: Where is the NTA? Officials interviewed from these barangays say they expect an annual NTA increase, so what they received in 2022 is simply part of what they should have received. Furthermore, he expounded that for those living on the mainland, especially those classified as urban barangays, the NTAs are not enough. The increase is not commensurate with the functions they must perform and the services they must deliver."

This implies that despite higher coffers that will be given to the LGUs, it is not enough for them to cater all devolved functions and services to them because they not only lack funds but also the capacity of their personnel to provide the needs of their constituents, which requires a lot of money. These trainings or seminars alone are a lavish to their funds, as a Barangay chairman shared:

The Punong Barangays were already complaining because they had no resources. We have to pay registration na Php 50 000 per head, and the attendees would include 11 people. Oh, 11 times 15 000 for one training only. Sabi ng ibang Kapitan, 'wala na kaming pag kukunan, sagad na yung appropriation naming' (*Another barangay chairman said, 'We do not have funds anymore; we have already maxed out our appropriation*). So, they have to look for some sources. Remember, the COA is very strict about that. The COA is also a department that comes in two ways. If you spend and do not liquidate, you're in hot waters. You are also in hot waters if you appropriate an amount and don't spend. Yes, if you don't spend the amount, and here comes the

audit, 'My goodness, you are depriving the people of the services for the appropriated amount.' I spent the appropriate amount, and I failed to liquidate it. You can be guilty of malversation, etc. So, there is no way to go straight and do what is best.

Meanwhile, Manalo, Estrada & Baluyot (2021) determined that some LGUs remain fiscally under-capacitated and, thus, will continue to need the National Government's support. Since the Growth Equity Fund (GEF) is aimed at bridging gaps in funding among LGUs (particularly targeted to support PAPs for and lagging LGUs) to gradually enable them to efficiently implement devolved functions and services—the nature, components, and mechanisms by which the GEF achieves stated objectives deserve scrutiny.

The GEF was according to Section 8 of Executive Order 138 and Rule XIII of its Implementing Rules and Regulation. The GEF was for the LGUs that are financially incapable of allocating funds and are technically weak in implementing devolved services (i.e., LGUs with high poverty incidences and low financial capacity). While there might be this kind of fund, it is worth taking note that it was only included in the proposed Fiscal Year (FY) 2022 national budget and continued until 2023, wherein by now, there is no assurance that in the following years, there still be GEFs to be included in the national budget. Gita-Carlos (2023) cited that according to the Department of Budget and Management, LGUs nationwide are expected to receive about Php 1.008 trillion in 2024, equivalent to 17.5 percent of the proposed FY 2024 national budget. As to Budget Secretary Amenah Pangandaman, this allocation pertains mainly to statutory shares of LGUs from national taxes, such as the National Tax Allotment (NTA) and the BARMM (Bangsamoro Autonomous Region in Muslim Mindanao) Annual Block Grant, among others. With this, there is no information on the GEF of those LGUs who claimed to be under-capacitated—a concern of how the GEF will be distributed because almost everyone is said to need it because their funds are insufficient.

Numerous areas need to be considered first before the full implementation of the Mandanas Ruling. Little things in the process need further scrutiny, especially on how they will fund all their PAPs, as well as those devolved functions and services from the Local Government Code of the Philippines while needing to have more personnel and trying to train them one by one. Thus, it is necessary to extend its transition period. Cruz (2023) cited that the Department of Interior and Local Government recommended that more responsibilities be moved from 2024 to 2027. However, on May 19 last year, President Ferdinand Marcos teased the new executive order (EO) on Mandanas Ruling to strengthen coordination partnership between national and local government, which the president said would be out by the year-end of 2023. But almost a year had passed, and no new EO remains.

B. Finance follows Responsibilities (Higher Responsibility)

Due to the National Government's budget cut to services, they required the full devolution of functions and services, which comes with a higher responsibility for the Local Government Units, which can be expected as a consequence of the LGU's call for higher funds in which the National Government had responded to.

Some barangay officials recognize several responses regarding the higher responsibilities, and the researchers observed two sub-themes, namely, perceived strict implementation requirements from the national government and unclear functions.

A barangay secretary perceives that one of the disadvantages in the implementation of the Mandanas Ruling may be the strictness that they may encounter from the National Government in their future affairs, "sa cons siguro syempre kapag na-implement yun baka masyado naming istriktuhan ng government natin sa mga kailangan naming i-provide, yung mga requirements na kumbaga minsan may mga requirements na hindi nila kayang i-produce sa Local Government Unit para mai-pass don sa National o Provincial whatsoever" (*For its cons, if the Mandanas Ruling is already implemented, there's a possibility that the National Government will become more strict with those things we need to provide, the requirements, for instance, that sometimes we cannot produce in the Local Government Unit, in which we are supposed to submit in the National or Provincial, whatsoever*).

Manalo et al. (2021) said that the full devolution of functions, along with the concomitant transition, entails both fiscal and PAP implementation issues, which can impact fiscal sustainability, service delivery, and the achievement of national objectives. More so, Panay News (2022) cited Atty. Ade Santillan Fajardo, the former national president of the Integrated Bar of the Philippines (IBP), explained that once the functions of national government agencies are devolved, LGUs will have to do more. In health services, for example, hiring healthcare workers and managing local hospitals will now become the LGUs' responsibility. Meanwhile, Pamintuan (2023) said, "Even before the Mandanas Ruling went into effect, several LGU officials were already grouching that despite the additional share in national revenues, they would be hard-pressed to perform all the devolved functions."

However, one significant issue may be the concern of another secretary, who raised the issue that “unclear functions” are devolved to them. Meanwhile, a barangay chairman was likewise concerned that “if the Punong Barangay does not understand what he is doing, I do not know what will happen to the barangay.”

Manalo, Estrada & Baluyot (2021) said that “to mitigate the fiscal impact of the SC ruling on the Mandanas-Garcia petition, the NG has decided to fully devolve LGC-mandated functions which many NGAs continue to implement at present. The NG sets forth this direction by issuing National Budget Memorandum (NBM) No. 138 and EO 138, as well as LBM 82, s. 2021. The Implementing Rules and Regulations (IRR) of EO 138 was subsequently issued last July 2, 2021.”

While there may be information regarding the devolved functions and services to the LGUs, they lack the necessary details to understand the Mandanas Ruling best. They may be familiar with the Ruling, but barangay officials must take the initiative to learn more about the basic aspects of the Ruling, duly noting that they are the implementers, especially at the grassroots levels—it is an essential part of their responsibilities.

C. Responsibilities follow Furnishing (Pieces of training or Seminars)

With now having bigger functions and higher responsibilities, it is perceived that along with their goal of strengthening their financial capacity is the most salient point to achieve the best of Mandanas Ruling—the capacitation of its personnel who will be the frontliners of the functions and services devolved to the LGUs.

Multiple responses were also observed regarding their lack of training or seminars regarding the Mandanas Ruling itself, which they believe is necessary to implement better. Nine barangay officials said they lack training or seminars to understand the ruling better. Furthermore, the researchers noted five sub-themes categorized as lack of training and seminars, inability to understand Devolution Transition Plans, failure to read Mandanas Ruling, necessary augmentation of manpower, and no new pieces of training or seminars since the newly elected have seated in power.

A barangay kagawad expressed that there needs to train them more, “kailangan pa naming magkaroon sana ng another training para ma-refresh, kasi bago na yung Secretary of Barangay, lalo na yung mga Kapitan bago na rin. Magkaron kami ng training then siguro seminar para mas maintindihan namin yang Mandanas Ruling” (*We need to have another training to be refreshed, because Barangay secretaries are new, especially barangay chairmen, they are new. We need training, and maybe, seminar for us to understand Mandanas Ruling*). It is needed, as he furthered, “hindi ko maintindihan, yung sa Devolution Transition Plans ng mga made-devolve talaga sa amin lalo na sa health services” (*I do not understand, those to be devolved in the Devolution Transition Plan, especially in health services*). Similarly, a Sangguninag Kabataan chairman admitted, “hindi ko pa siya kasi totally nabasa kasi eh busy pa kasi. Hindi ko pa po talaga siya na-review” (*I did not really find time to read it because I am still busy. I actually did not review it yet*).

Additionally, another Barangay kagawad said:

Karamihan eh kasi wala pang seminar yung iba about diyan [patungkol sa Mandanas Ruling]. Doon sa Second Barangay Congress talagang in-attend ko ‘yun sa Baguio. Ako lang nag-attend [sa aming barangay] kaya lang ‘di ko kasi masyadong naintindihan ‘yan eh kasi nandoon, andami kasi. Kasi nag-iisa lang kasi ako kaya hindi ako masyadong nakikinig, wala akong kasama eh (*Almost everyone has no seminars attended yet [regarding the Mandanas Ruling]. In the Second Barangay Congress, I really urged to attend that in Baguio. I am the only who attended [from our barangay], but I did not really understand it, it’s just too much for me. I was just alone and I was not really listening because I am alone*).

With these, it is pointed out by a barangay kagawad that along with the functions and services devolved requires more manpower to cater to its needs; thus, “the need to augment manpower who have the basic skills” which still needs to equip with proper knowledge on how to implement the devolved services.

Licayan (2022) stated that despite such legislation, many local government units are still wary of this devolution for many reasons. The first one is the capacity of LGUs to carry out such functions. Many local governments have differing capacities and circumstances regarding efficiency and fiscal capacity. Some LGUs expressed that devolution of functions requires planning and execution, giving rise to service delivery challenges. The preparation of plans is a tedious process that requires technical expertise. Given the size of local bureaucracy and the availability of personnel, such a process will lead to inefficiency.

It can be gleaned that there are still many things that the LGUs need to prepare for the full implementation of the Mandanas Ruling. One of them is to have intensive capacity-building for the local government officials and other personnel regarding the respective tasks they need to fulfil in various fields of services.

Ta-asan (2023) cited that the Department of Budget and Management said a Php 28.9-billion Local Government Support Fund will be deployed for capacity-building projects ahead of the imminent devolution of National Government (NG) services. Subsequently, Budget Secretary Pangadaman said, “We will formulate

capacity-building training and seminars for our LGUs (local government units) to help them—so that by the time we have full devolution, they can stand on their own feet.”

However, when asked about the conduct of training or seminars since the start of their term, a barangay kagawad said, “Wala pa po. Noong 2021 pa ‘yun nangyari. Matagal na” (*There is none yet. The last time was in 2021. It’s been years*).

Training and seminars are non-negotiable and can be conducted immediately by the concerned National Government Agencies because there is still no extension in the Mandanas Rulings’ transition period. There is a need for the LGUs to double-time because the time is still running, and they have to be capacitated no matter how difficult it may be for them because the Mandanas Ruling is already final. Sooner or later, they need to provide the functions and services devolved to them.

D. Furnishing follows Accountability (Misuse of Funds)

To the proponents of the Mandanas-Garcia Ruling, it was a beautiful, flawless idea that urged them to call for it in the Supreme Court. However, it must be duly noted that it may, sooner or later, become an avenue of abuse of power and money, especially at the local level. There may be greater competition for each post because there will be more funds for the LGUs, which involves the barangay officials. Therefore, it can only be that beautiful, flawless idea if there is an integration of accountability to all of these implementers.

Collected responses reveal that there may be misuse of funds in LGUs, which could result in abuses in the local governance. The researchers have identified four sub-themes: misconception of the Mandanas Ruling, prevalent corruption, mismanagement of funds, and skepticism of the implementers’ intent.

One proof can be the current notion of the barangay officials of their higher honorarium that will be received along with their personnel. It is alarming, especially since it is one of the greatest numbers of answers when asked about how the Mandanas Ruling affects the economic development of their barangay. A barangay kagawad shared:

Kapag epekto yung Mandanas Ruling, marami talaga ang mabibigyan ng maganda. Oo, marami talaga. Lahat ng mga staff namin, imbes na yung honorarium nila, for example yung bantay bayan namin ay Php 2,500, kapag meron na yung Mandanas Ruling magiging triple pa yung honorarium nila. Para naman yung ano nila, public servant magiging masipag naman sila sa pagtra-trabaho diba? Kaya namang SK naman ngayon, SK Kagawad, dati walang sahod, ngayon may sahod na kaya, konti man yung sahod nila, kahit kunti-konti, nag tra-trabaho naman sila (*If the Mandanas Ruling will take effect, there will be a lot of benefits. There’s really a lot. All the staff, instead of their honorarium...for example, our Bantay Bayan [honorarium] is Php 2,500, with the Mandanas Ruling, it will be tripled. It is a compensation for their public service, and for them to work harder, right? Our SK, SK Kagawad, before they do not have a salary, now they already receive compensation, even if it may only be a small amount, they are still fulfilling their duties*).

Furthermore, a barangay chairman said, “yung problema namin talaga may corruption talaga na nangyayari” (*the problem is that there really is corruption happening*). More so, he said that, “yung [hindi] paggamit ng pondo na maayos... mapupunta lang sa wala” (*if there’s a misuse of funds...it will only go to waste*). Another Barangay chairman have said, “maganda ang Mandanas Ruling, subalit ang mga taong nagpapatupad ang nagiging problema” (*Mandanas Ruling is supposed to be good, but those implementers are sometimes the problem*).

Pamintuan (2023) cited “Interior and Local Government Secretary Benhur Abalos, who says the problem is worse in fourth to sixth-class municipalities that lack legal officers or experts with knowledge about laws on government procurement and auditing, graft and corruption, ease of doing business and even local autonomy. Inefficiency and corruption can become entrenched in some areas, whether willfully or inadvertently, due to weak capacity for governance.”

It is evident that due to misconceptions about the ruling, one may take a grip on one's position, and/or aspirants would battle for themselves to overthrow the one in position. If this will be permitted to remain as a notion in society, and considering that sooner or later, the Mandanas Ruling will be implemented full-blown, there may be a case of amassing funds in the most discreet way. There are many ways to do that because it is still prevalent in the Philippines, even though Sandiganbayan tries to decide criminal and civil cases against government officials and employees accused of graft corruption and other similar offenses. Even those in position right now are alarmed by the possible effect of the Mandanas Ruling once implemented—that it might be an avenue or perpetuation of corruption. Indeed, officials today are aware that there are cases of lacking accountability for their actions that threaten transparency to their constituents. Therefore, with the Mandanas Ruling, there should be a strict mechanism to evaluate and check the affairs of the LGUs, which comes from the national government, to oversee the implementation of the Ruling. Wherein according to Shah (2014), “Local government performance accountability requires four types of assessments: (a) their compliance with

due process and law; (b) monitoring of fiscal health for sustainability; (c) monitoring of service delivery; and (d) citizens' satisfaction with local services." Accountability is a basic and bare minimum characteristic deserved by the ones who trusted these barangay officials and enjoyed their power and privileges. Supposedly, it is not demanded but must be fairly given.

Meanwhile, it is also worth noting that most respondent barangays are NTA-dependent. Thus, if the implementation of the ruling is tainted by abuse, then projects, activities, and programs will not only be victimized by budget cuts but also by devolved functions and services, which will be compromised.

Research Question 5: What are the expected outputs to help barangay officials of Solano, Nueva Vizcaya in their level of understanding and perceived challenges to the Mandanas Ruling?

The researchers proposed two outputs at the end of this study to help the barangay officials better understand the Mandanas Ruling as a first step to its full implementation. First, the researchers will post online and distribute an infographic with the basic information about the Mandanas Ruling to give the respondents and other individuals who will reach the post an overview of the matter to break their initial understanding that revolves around their honorarium that will be higher, and not the funds of the barangay itself that will be higher along with their responsibility due to the functions and services devolved to them. Second, the researchers will craft a PowerPoint presentation containing the details and information about the Ruling, which will be distributed to the barangay officials of Solano, Nueva Vizcaya. This may be utilized to discuss the matter during their barangay sessions or if they opt to conduct a seminar regarding the Mandanas Ruling. Furthermore, the researchers will also send these outputs to the Municipality of Solano and the Department of Interior and Local Government, suggesting that they may conduct a seminar, training, and workshop for all their personnel and barangay officials to equip them with a better understanding for a better implementation of the Mandanas Ruling.

Ethical Considerations

The study adhered to strict ethical standards throughout its conduct. The researchers declared no conflict of interest, ensuring that all data obtained from respondents were used solely for academic purposes, knowledge advancement, and as a reference for future studies. Confidentiality and data protection were strictly observed by withholding any identifying information of participants, and all collected data, whether in paper or digital form, were securely destroyed upon completion of the study. Participants were informed of their right to refuse or withdraw from the study at any point, particularly if they felt vulnerable to any potential risks, with the researchers prioritizing their safety and well-being at all times. Although no physical risks were involved, some questionnaire items related to transparency and accountability of public officials may have posed minimal sensitivity; thus, participation was entirely voluntary, supported by signed informed consent forms. These forms clearly outlined the purpose of the study, the basis for participant selection, and assurances of confidentiality and protection. The benefits of the study include providing valuable insights into the level of understanding among barangay officials, which may inform improved policy implementation in fiscal governance. Furthermore, the terms of reference specify that the manuscript is jointly owned by the university, the authors, and the research adviser as co-author. The dissemination of findings was carried out through the distribution of an infographic and a PowerPoint presentation to the Municipal Budget Officer, the Department of the Interior and Local Government, and the concerned barangays of Solano, Nueva Vizcaya, to support policy understanding and serve as reference material for future engagements.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, several key conclusions were drawn. The respondents are relatively young in service and have had limited exposure to seminars related to the Mandanas Ruling and fiscal devolution. Despite this, they demonstrated a general familiarity with the Mandanas Ruling, particularly in terms of transition planning and revenue and fiscal matters. Statistical analysis revealed that respondents' positions, years of service, and number of seminars attended do not significantly influence their level of understanding, except in the area of revenue and fiscal matters, where seminar participation plays a crucial role due to the technical nature of the subject. Furthermore, four major themes emerged as perceived challenges in the full implementation of the Mandanas Ruling: budgetary constraints (plans follow finance), increased responsibilities (finance follows responsibilities), lack of sufficient training (responsibilities follow furnishing), and concerns on accountability, particularly the misuse of funds (furnishing follows accountability). Lastly, the study found that most barangays are highly dependent on the National Tax Allotment (NTA) and lack income-generating initiatives, which presents a significant challenge as they assume additional devolved functions and services previously managed by the national government.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, several recommendations are proposed to enhance the implementation of the Mandanas Ruling and strengthen local governance. It is recommended that future assessments include not only the highest- and lowest-income barangays but also middle-income barangays to better understand existing gaps across varying economic levels. To improve local operations, barangay officials are encouraged to actively revisit and discuss their transition plans and, where feasible, consult or involve previous proponents of these plans, particularly from prior terms. The conduct of more intensive, engaging, and accessible (preferably free or low-cost) training and seminars on the Mandanas Ruling is strongly advised, with mandatory participation among barangay officials to enhance their technical knowledge, particularly in revenue and fiscal matters. Additionally, an immediate review of Executive Order No. 138, series of 2021, is recommended, considering the conclusion of the transition period for full devolution in 2024. Government agencies tasked with monitoring local government units should also strengthen their oversight mechanisms to mitigate potential risks of misuse of funds and abuse of authority, given the expanded responsibilities and increased fiscal resources under the ruling. Furthermore, the development of improved criteria for assessing under-capacitated local government units is suggested, particularly in relation to the allocation and continued inclusion of the Growth Equity Fund in future fiscal budgets. Lastly, future researchers are encouraged to explore additional variables and contexts, including municipal and provincial local government units, levels of dependence on the National Tax Allotment, and varying local government profiles, to provide a more comprehensive understanding of the Mandanas Ruling's implementation.

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